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**Understanding Last-Mile Learners' Motivation in
English Language Learning Toward Developing
the MOTIVE Framework**

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ABSTRACT

Motivation plays a crucial role in successful language learning, especially among last-mile learners who face distinct barriers due to geographic isolation and limited access to educational resources. This study aims to understand the key factors influencing English language learning motivation among last-mile learners, serving as a foundation for developing the MOTIVE Framework. The participants, primarily female students aged 13 to 14, predominantly speak Cebuano as their heritage language and prefer Filipino as the medium of instruction. Many come from low socioeconomic backgrounds typical of last-mile communities. Findings reveal that students' motivation is shaped by a range of personal and contextual factors, with varied associations observed. Pearson's correlation analysis indicates no significant relationship between age and personal factors. Gender and grade level show some correlations with motivational components, but these are not consistent. Other sociodemographic variables, such as heritage language, preferred medium of instruction, parents' education, occupation, and income, generally show no significant correlation with motivation. These results highlight the need for learner-centered approaches that address individual experiences, preferences, and challenges in order to foster motivation and support English language learning among last-mile learners.

Keywords: *English Language Learning, Heritage Language, Motivational Factor, Socioeconomic Status*

Introduction

Language is the foundation of all communication and the primary medium through which thoughts are expressed (Khan, 2017). Among the many languages spoken worldwide, English stands out as a global lingua franca essential for education, commerce, and international exchange. Despite the various strategies employed by educators, teaching English remains a challenging endeavor—particularly in remote settings—due to learners' varying attitudes and levels of motivation (Domingo, 2020).

Stephen Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis posits that motivation is one of the key affective variables that significantly influences second language acquisition, alongside anxiety and self-confidence (Krashen, 1982). Whether intrinsic or extrinsic, motivation fuels learners' engagement, persistence, and eventual success in mastering language skills (Zhao, 2012). Motivated learners are more likely to participate actively and achieve academic gains, while those who lack motivation often

show diminished effort and poorer performance.

Sustaining learners' motivation, however, is particularly difficult in marginalized and underserved contexts. Last-mile learners—those studying in geographically isolated schools with limited access to educational resources—face added layers of difficulty that affect their drive to learn (UNESCO, 2020). These challenges include socioeconomic struggles, lack of parental support, and inadequate exposure to the English language. Understanding what drives or hinders motivation in these contexts is essential for meaningful educational intervention.

This study was conducted in Hinandayan National High School, a last-mile school located in the mountainous area of Nasipit, Agusan del Norte. As a remote public secondary school, it represents a learning environment where motivational factors are likely influenced by a complex mix of personal, teacher-related, and parental elements. While previous research (e.g., Ayub, 2010; Nguyen, 2019) has addressed student motivation in general, little attention has been paid to how these factors operate in last-mile contexts, particularly in English language learning.

Thus, the primary aim of this study is to explore the underlying factors affecting the English language learning motivation of learners in this context. Specifically, it describes the demographic profile of learners and examines whether these profiles have significant relationships with key motivational factors. The findings are intended to inform stakeholders—including teachers, parents, school heads, and curriculum developers—on how to better foster motivation among last-mile learners. Moreover, this study serves as a foundation for developing the MOTIVE Model Framework, a contextualized and responsive approach to enhancing learner motivation in similar educational environments.

Theoretical Framework

There were three motivational theories anchored in this study, namely: Attribution Theory, Self-Determination Theory, and Self-efficacy Theory. These theories provide a framework to better understand the factors that influence learners' English learning motivation.

Attribution Theory (B. Weiner)

According to Weiner (2010), Attribution theory is concerned with the perceived causes of success and failure for both the self and others. It assumes that people want to understand why an event or behavior occurred (Hopper, 2018). For instance, when people fail to perform a certain task, they would attribute it to a certain thing and/or others. In the context of the learners, according to this theory, learners tend to explain their reasons for success or failure based upon three attributions and one of these is internal

or external attribution.

In the study conducted by Mohammadi and Sharififar (2016), it was found that EFL students attribute their achievements to external more than internal factors in the process of learning English. The results of their study also revealed that there were significant differences between males and females in ability as an internal attribution and luck as an external attribution, wherein, male students tend to attribute their success and failure to ability more than female students while females attribute their success and failures to luck more than male learners.

Self-Determination Theory

Self-determination Theory was developed by Edward Deci and Richard Ryan. According to Deci and Ryan (2012), Self-determination Theory (SDT) is an empirically derived theory of human motivation and personality in social contexts that differentiates motivation in terms of being autonomous and controlled. This theory can be incorporated into teaching through various strategies such as supporting autonomy, encouraging relatedness, and cultivating competence.

According to Niemiec and Ryan (2009), self-determination theory (SDT) assumes that inherent in human nature is the propensity to be curious about one's environment and interested in learning and developing one's knowledge. For instance, one may want to learn how to speak a particular language including the grammatical rules and the correct way of pronouncing the words of that language. It also suggests that people are motivated to grow and change by three innate and universal psychological needs, namely: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Hence, in the context of the learners, the teachers need to discover and apply various ways to help the learners meet these psychological needs.

Self-efficacy Theory

The concept of Self-efficacy was developed by Albert Bandura. Bandura (2000) believes that self-efficacy is the confidence in one's ability to plan and carry out the strategies necessary to manage potential situations. It emphasizes an individual's confidence in their ability to complete a task or achieve a goal (Hopper, 2021). Hence, when learners lack confidence in their abilities, they would not be able to perform their tasks and or master their skills.

According to Cherry (2022), self-efficacy is important because it plays a role in how we feel about ourselves and whether or not we successfully achieve our goals in life. People with a strong sense of self-efficacy develop a deeper interest in the activities in which they participate while people

with a weak sense of self-efficacy believe that difficult tasks and situations are beyond their capabilities. In the context of the learners, if they don't have the belief in their capability to perform a certain task, they would certainly fail to execute the skills and/or competencies expected from them.

By integrating these three motivational theories, this study sought to understand the factors influencing learners' motivation to learn English and how educators can help the learners overcome the challenges to enhance their learning experience.

Method

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to examine the extent of motivation among last-mile learners in English language learning, with particular focus on the contributing factors—namely personal, teacher-related, and parental influences. The insights generated from this investigation will serve as a basis for developing the MOTIVE Model Framework.

Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Describe the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, grade level, heritage language, preferred medium of instruction, parents' educational attainment, occupation, and combined monthly income;
2. Determine the extent of motivation of the last-mile learners in learning the English language
3. Examine the relationship between learners' demographic profile and the extent of their English language learning motivation.

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. The study utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire which consisted of two parts. Part 1 determined the demographic profile of the participants in terms of age, sex, grade level, heritage language, preferred medium of instruction, and the socioeconomic status of the parents. On the other hand, part 2 identified the extent of students' motivation.

Participants

There were 140 Junior High School students at Hinandayan National High School Main Campus. For administrative considerations, only 75% of the total population were included as participants, resulting

in a sample size of 105 students. To ensure representation from each grade level, stratified sampling was employed. The researcher obtained the list of students from each Grade Level Adviser and assigned codes to each student's name. Participants were then randomly selected by drawing these codes, with the drawn names considered as the study participants.

Table 1. Sample Population

Grade Level	Population	Sample
7	35	26
8	30	23
9	36	27
10	39	29
TOTAL	140	105

Research Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire which consists of two parts. The first part was all about the demographic profile of the participants which contained the respondents' age, gender, mother tongue and others. The second part was all about the factors of language learning motivation, namely: personal factors, teachers' influence, and parental influence. Before formulating the research questionnaire, the researcher first reads different researches to ensure that the questions to be formulated are appropriate and relevant.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the research questionnaire, the researcher submitted a copy of the self-made questionnaire to the panel of experts whose expertise are relevant to English language teaching. After retrieving comments and suggestions from the experts, the researcher revised the questionnaire. It was then pilot-tested to 32 students. The data were tallied and analyzed by a statistician for its reliability coefficient. The result of the reliability test shows that the research instrument is reliable.

Results and discussion

Objective 1. Demographic profile of the participants

Figure 1. Personal Profile distribution (%) of the participants.

Figure 1 shows the demographic profile of the participants in terms of age, gender, grade level, heritage language and preferred medium of instruction.

In terms of age, it can be seen that 40.95% of the participants are ages 13-14. It is followed by ages 15-16 which is 38.1%. It can also be noted that 13.33% are below 13 years old while only 7.62% are ages 17 and above. This implies that majority of the participants are still young and are very much motivated to go to school in order to learn.

In terms of gender, it is notable that 59.05% of the participants are females while only 40.95% are males. Ritchie (2019) reported that in every country, births are male-based, hence, it is expected that males will also dominate the schools in terms of population. However, in this study, the majority of the participants are females. One possible reason for this is the gender stereotypes held by various stakeholder groups in foreign language schools (Davis-Kean et al., 2021).

In terms of grade level, we can see that 27.62% of the participants are from Grade 10. It is followed by Grade 9 which is 25.71%. On the other hand, 24.76% of participants are Grade 7 while only 21.91% are from Grade 8. This implies that majority of the participants are dominated by the

Grade 10 students.

In terms of heritage language, we can see that Cebuano is the heritage language of the majority of the students which is 72.38% while Higaonon as their heritage language is 22.86%. On the other hand, only 4.76% are of Filipino Heritage. Noels (2005) found that heritage language learners were more likely to learn German than non-heritage language learners because it was a significant part of their self-concept. Similarly, the participants of this study will more likely to learn English because it is an essential part of their education process as well.

In terms of the preferred medium of instruction, it can be noted that 47.62% of the participants prefer Filipino as their medium of instruction. It is followed by English which is 25.71%. On the other hand, 20.95% prefers the use of Cebuano while only 5.71% prefers Higaonon. This implies that the students have their language preferences in learning and it can be noted that the majority's preferred medium is Filipino. This finding is in consonance with what Soruç and Griffiths (2018) stated in the study they conducted about English as a medium of instruction: Students' strategies. Findings of the study revealed that students try to learn the subject matter by means of using a non-native language. Thus, language teachers have to consider these preferences because effective language teaching and learning can only be achieved when teachers are aware of their learners' needs, capabilities, potentials, and preferences in meeting these needs (Bada and Okan, 2000).

Figure 2. Socioeconomic status of the parents

Figure 2 shows the socioeconomic status of the parents. In terms of the highest educational attainment of the parents, 47.62% of the mothers are elementary level, thus indicating that they did not finish the basic education while only 0.95% of them were able to finish college. On the other hand, it is shown that the majority or 65.71% of the fathers have only reached elementary level while none of them was able to finish college. This finding implies that the parents' educational attainment can affect the behavior and attitude of the students at school. This is in consonance to the findings of Davis-Kean et al. (2021) which revealed that parental educational attainment lays a foundation for children's academic success by way of the expectations and beliefs that parents have for them, as well as the mental stimulation that parents offer both inside and outside the home.

In terms of the parents' occupation, it can be seen that the majority or 59.05% of the mothers are working as farmers, 24.76% are doing business while 16.19% are housewives. On the other hand, the figure shows that the majority or 90.48% of the fathers are working as farmers, 4.76% are doing business, while 4.76% are not working. The majority's occupation implies that they rely on agriculture. When farming fails, there is a tendency that they won't be able to provide for their children. As a result, this could affect their children's motivation and self-concept. This finding is similar to the result of the study conducted by Khan (2017), wherein, it was found that children's self-concept was consistently and favorably impacted by their parents' occupation.

In terms of the combined monthly income, it can be seen that the majority or 94.29% of the parents are earning an amount lesser than ₱10,957.00 which can be considered as a low income. When parents have a low income, providing for the educational needs of their children would be difficult. This finding supports the claim of Zahid and Ashfaq (2022) wherein they emphasized that the role of parents' income is the most crucial factor in the process of learning English language as the learners spend most of their time with their parents since childhood. Furthermore, in the study conducted by Buriro et al. (2015), it was found that the higher the socio-economic status and the more stable a student's socio-economic background, the more motivated they were to learn English. However, in this study, the majority's socioeconomic status can be described as low.

Objective 2. Extent of language learning motivation of the students

Table 2. Mean distribution of the extent of language learning motivation

Personal Factors		Extent of motivation		Interpretation
Indicators		Mean	Description	
1	I consider the English language interesting and challenging to learn.	4.32	Agree	High
2	I enjoy listening to English language discussions.	4.24	Agree	High
3	I like to speak English while interacting with other people.	3.50	Agree	High
4	The English language allows me to freely express	3.15	Neither agree	Moderate

	my thoughts or opinions, or both about a certain issue.		nor disagree	
5	Studying the English language helps me get ahead of others.	3.29	Neither agree nor disagree	Moderate
6	By learning English, I can pass tests which will give me opportunities to work abroad.	4.18	Agree	High
7	I become confident to speak when using English language.	3.32	Neither agree nor disagree	Moderate
8	I become confident to write using the English language.	3.43	Neither agree nor disagree	Moderate
9	I want to improve my communication skills using the English language.	3.84	Agree	High
10	I want to learn English in order to communicate with those who speak English.	4.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
11	I want to learn English because it is the main medium of instruction of all educational levels.	4.67	Strongly Agree	Very high
12	Learning English helps me improve my vocabulary.	4.65	Strongly Agree	Very High
13	Learning English would help improve my reading comprehension skills.	4.48	Agree	High
14	Learning English makes me proud of myself.	4.41	Agree	High
15	Learning English helps me become a critical thinker.	3.90	Agree	High
Overall Weighted Mean		4.00	Agree	High

Range of means: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Uncertain; 3.50-4.49 Agree; 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree

Table 2 shows the mean distribution of the extent of learners' language learning motivation in terms of personal factors.

As gleaned from the table, it can be noted that indicator 11, which states that learners want to learn English because it is the main medium of instruction of all educational levels, garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.67 which can be interpreted as very high. This shows that learners are very motivated to learn English because they know that English is not only a subject taught at school but also a medium used in teaching. This also implies that learners are aware of the importance of English in their education.

These findings supported Bani-Khaled's (2014) study noting that students believe that learning English is an important part of their education. However, in the study conducted by Kırkgöz (2014) about Students' perceptions of English language versus Turkish language used as the medium of instruction, it was found that students have difficulty in understanding disciplinary knowledge and in understanding specific details when the medium of instruction used is English.

Second to the highest is indicator 12 which states that learning English helps improve the learners' knowledge of vocabulary. This indicator has a weighted mean of 4.65 which can be described as very high. This shows that the learners believe that learning English would help them improve their

knowledge of vocabulary.

On the other hand, indicator 4 which states that English language allows the learners to freely express their thoughts or opinions, or both about a certain issue got the lowest weighted mean of 3.15 interpreted as moderately motivating. This implies that learners have the desire to express their opinions through English but are having difficulties or challenges in doing. This finding supports the result of the study conducted by Horne (2010) on students' reflections on the expression of opinions in discussion in English wherein, students were found to be able to voice their opinions, but there was a gap between what they wanted to say and how much they were actually able to say and create a discussion.

The overall weighted mean of the extent of motivation of the students in terms of personal factors is 4.00 which can be interpreted as high. This means that the learners are personally motivated to learn English because they are aware of the importance and benefits of learning English. This is also a manifestation that they wanted to develop competence among themselves.

According to the study conducted by Sengkey et al. (2018), the preference of students to learn English was possibly related to their future success prospects. Self-determination theory explains that three basic universal psychological needs—autonomy, competence, and relatedness—drive human growth and change. Thus, there is no doubt why the student-participants in this study have high personal motivation and determination to learn English because they felt that learning English would help them to be competent in communicating English for future significant linkages.

Objective 3. Significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and the factors affecting their English language learning motivation

Table 3. Significant relationship between age and the extent of language learning motivation

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient ^a	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Age	Extent of motivation	-0.006	0.955	Very weak and negative	Not significant

*Legend: ^a tested using Pearson's r correlation test; -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$*

Table 3 shows the significant relationship between the age and the extent of learners' motivation.

As shown in the table, age and the extent of motivation have a very weak and negative relationship and are not statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. This suggests that as learners grow older, their motivation to learn English tends to decrease. This finding is consistent with the results of the study conducted by Bećirović and Hurić-Bećirović (2017), which found that ten-year-old students exhibited the highest motivation for learning English as a second language, whereas eighteen-year-olds showed the lowest.

Similarly, Ghenghesh (2010) found that students' motivation to learn a second language declines with age, attributing this decline to teaching practices and lesson content. These insights highlight the importance of teachers employing engaging and responsive strategies to help sustain students' motivation as they progress in age.

Table 4. Significant Relationship between gender and the extent of language learning motivation

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient ^a	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Gender (Female)	Extent of motivation	0.069	0.485	Very weak and positive	Not significant

*Legend: ^a tested using Point-biserial correlation test (Pearson's r); -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$*

Table 4 shows the significant relationship between the sex and the extent of learners' motivation.

As presented in the table, the extent of motivation among the dominant gender is not statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.05$, with a very weak and positive relationship, indicated by a p-value of 0.485. This finding aligns with the study of Becirovic (2017), which revealed that gender has a significant effect on students' motivation to learn English—specifically, female students were found to be more motivated to learn English as a foreign language compared to male students.

However, this contrasts with the findings of Zayyana et al. (2022), which showed that male students generally exhibit higher levels of intrinsic and integrative motivation than female students.

Table 5. Significant Relationship between grade level and the extent of language learning motivation

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient ^a	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Grade level	Extent of motivation	-0.126	0.199	Weak and negative	Not significant

*Legend: ^a tested using Pearson's r correlation test; -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$*

Table 5 shows the significant relationship between the grade level and the extent of motivation along with personal, teacher, and parental factors.

As shown in Table 7, the grade level of the students and the extent of their motivation have a weak and negative relationship, with a correlation coefficient of -0.126, and this relationship is not statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.05$.

This result aligns with the findings of Nayir (2017), which revealed that tenth-grade students exhibited higher levels of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation compared to twelfth-grade students, while eleventh-grade students demonstrated greater motivation than both tenth and twelfth graders.

Table 6. *Significant Relationship between heritage language and the extent of language learning motivation*

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient ^a	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Heritage language (Cebuano)	Extent of motivation	-0.024	0.806	Very weak and negative	Not significant
Heritage language (Higaonon)	Extent of motivation	0.071	0.472	Very weak and positive	Not significant

*Legend: ^a tested using Point-biserial correlation test (Pearson's r); -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$.*

Table 6 shows the significant relationship between the heritage language and the extent of learners' motivation.

As shown above, the relationship between the Cebuano heritage language and the extent of learners' motivation is very weak and negative, with a correlation coefficient of -0.024, and is not statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Similarly, the relationship between the Higaonon heritage language and the extent of motivation is also very weak but positive, with a correlation coefficient of 0.071, and likewise not significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Overall, these results indicate that the learners' heritage language—

whether Cebuano or Higaonon—does not have a significant relationship with their motivation to learn English.

This suggests that learners are motivated to study English not because of their linguistic background, but rather due to the perceived benefits of learning the language or the positive experiences they gain from the learning process (Wen, 2011).

Table 7. Significant relationship between preferred medium of instruction and the extent of language learning motivation

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient ^a	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Preferred Medium of Instruction (English)	Extent of motivation	-0.050	0.610	Weak and negative	Not significant
Preferred Medium of Instruction (Cebuano)	Extent of motivation	0.035	0.724	Very weak and positive	Not significant
Preferred Medium of Instruction (Filipino)	Extent of motivation	-0.023	0.819	Very weak and positive	Not significant

*Legend: ^a tested using Point-biserial correlation test (Pearson's r); -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$*

Table 7 shows the significant relationship between the preferred medium of instruction and the extent of learners' motivation.

Based on the table above, the relationship between English as the preferred medium of instruction and the extent of motivation is weak, with a correlation coefficient of -0.050, and is not significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Similarly, the relationship between Cebuano as the preferred medium of

instruction and the extent of motivation is very weak and positive, with a correlation coefficient of 0.035, and also not significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Additionally, the relationship between Filipino as the preferred medium of instruction and the extent of motivation is very weak and negative, with a correlation coefficient of -0.023, and likewise not significant at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Overall, these findings suggest that students' preferred medium of instruction does not have a statistically significant relationship with their motivation to learn English. Nevertheless, they underscore the importance of recognizing learners' language preferences. Doing so can contribute to a more inclusive and responsive English language teaching and learning environment (Bada & Okan, 2000).

Table 8. Significant relationship between parents' educational attainment and the extent of language learning motivation

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient ^a	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Mother's educational attainment	Extent of motivation	0.033	0.738	Very weak and positive	Not significant
Father's educational attainment	Extent of motivation	-0.152	0.122	Weak and negative	Not significant

Legend: ^a tested using Pearson's *r* correlation test; -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$

Table 8 shows the significant relationship between the parents' educational attainment and the extent of learners' motivation.

Based on the projected data on mothers' educational attainment, its relationship with the extent of learners' motivation is very weak and positive, with a correlation coefficient of 0.033. In terms of fathers' educational attainment, the relationship is weak and negative, with a correlation coefficient of -0.152.

Overall, the educational attainment of the parents shows no statistically significant relationship with the extent of learners' motivation at $\alpha = 0.05$. This suggests that students' motivation to learn

English is not significantly influenced by their parents' level of education. This finding contrasts with the results of Iwaniec's (2020) study, which found that students whose parents had lower levels of education tended to be less motivated.

Table 9. Significant relationship between parents' occupation and the extent of language learning motivation

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient ^a	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Mother's Occupation (Farmer)	Extent of motivation	0.171	0.082	Weak and positive	Not significant
Father's Occupation (Farmer)	Extent of motivation	0.029	0.770	Very weak and positive	Not significant

Legend: ^a tested using Point-biserial correlation test (Pearson's *r*); -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$

Table 9 shows the significant relationship between the occupation of the parents' and the extent of motivation of the learners.

With regard to mothers' occupation, the table indicates a weak and positive relationship with the extent of motivation, with a correlation coefficient of 0.171. For fathers' occupation, the relationship is very weak and positive, with a correlation coefficient of 0.029.

Overall, both parents' occupations have no statistically significant relationship with the learners' extent of motivation at $\alpha = 0.05$. These findings align with the results of Arib (2017), who concluded that parents' occupation does not significantly influence students' motivation to learn English. This suggests that learners remain motivated regardless of their parents' professional backgrounds. However, this finding contradicts the study of Muslim et al. (2020), which found a significant relationship between students' motivation and their parents' occupation, indicating that occupational factors may influence learners' motivation in certain contexts.

Table 10. Significant relationship between the parents' combined monthly income and the extent of language learning motivation

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient ^a	p-value	Relationship	Significance
Combined HH monthly income	Extent of motivation	-0.024	0.809	Very weak and negative	Not significant

*Legend: ^a tested using Pearson's r correlation test; -1.0 to -0.5 or 1.0 to 0.5 strong relationship; -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5 moderate relationship; -0.3 to -0.1 or 0.1 to 0.3 weak relationship; -0.1 to 0.1 none or very weak relationship; * significant at $\alpha=0.05$*

Table 10 shows the significant relationship between the parents' combined monthly income and the extent of learners' motivation.

As shown in the table, the relationship between the parents' combined monthly income and the extent of motivation is very weak and negative, with a correlation coefficient of -0.024, and is not significant at $\alpha = 0.05$, with a p-value of 0.089. This indicates that the parents' income does not have a statistically significant relationship with the learners' motivation to learn English. Therefore, any observed variation in motivation cannot be confidently attributed to differences in household income.

This finding contradicts the study conducted by Melati (2019), which revealed a positive and significant correlation between socioeconomic status and students' learning motivation. In Melati's study, students from higher-income families tended to show higher levels of motivation. The inconsistency between the findings suggests that other contextual factors, such as cultural values or school support systems, may mediate the relationship between socioeconomic status and student motivation.

Objective 4: Hierarchical MOTIVE Framework

Rationale:

The MOTIVE Framework is grounded in the empirical findings of this study, which revealed the complex and multilayered factors influencing learners' motivation to learn English. At the foundation lies Multilingual Scaffolding (M), which recognizes the critical role of learners' heritage languages (such as Cebuano and Higaonon) and preferred instructional languages (Filipino) in building comprehension and reducing anxiety. This foundational level ensures learners feel linguistically supported before fully engaging with English.

Building on this, Opportunities for Translanguaging (O) encourage dynamic language use, allowing learners to fluidly navigate between languages, thus fostering deeper understanding and motivation. Recognizing the variability in learners' developmental stages, the framework incorporates

Tailored Interventions by Grade Level (T), which address motivational differences observed across grades, as indicated by the negative relationship between grade level and motivation.

Next, Individualized Learner Profiles (I) acknowledge that motivation is influenced by personal, familial, and socioeconomic contexts, such as parental occupation and income, which though weakly correlated, remain important considerations for targeted support. To further engage learners, Varied Motivational Strategies (V) are employed, integrating intrinsic and extrinsic motivators aligned with learners' backgrounds and preferences. Finally, Empowering Pedagogies (E) emphasize active learner engagement and teacher responsiveness to sustain motivation despite external challenges.

Together, the hierarchical structure of the MOTIVE Framework reflects the interconnectedness of language responsiveness, learner diversity, and contextual factors, providing educators with a practical roadmap to cultivate and maintain motivation in English language learning among diverse student populations.

Figure 3. MOTIVE Framework

Level 1: Foundation – Language Responsiveness

M – Multilingual Scaffolding- Provide initial support using learners' heritage language (Cebuano, Higaonon) and preferred medium of instruction (Filipino) to build understanding and reduce anxiety in English learning. This respects students' language preferences and creates an inclusive learning environment, even if heritage language does not significantly affect motivation statistically.

Level 2: Opportunity – Inclusive Instructional Practices

O – Opportunities for Translanguaging- Encourage teachers to integrate translanguaging strategies that allow learners to use multiple languages in English learning. This bridges gaps between students' linguistic backgrounds and English, promoting better comprehension and motivation.

Level 3: Tailoring – Developmental Appropriateness

T – Targeted Grade-Level Interventions- Address the weak negative relationship between grade

level and motivation by designing activities and teaching methods that are appropriate for different grade levels, sustaining motivation especially as learners advance in school.

Level 4: Individual Consideration – Learner Profiling

I – Individualized Motivation Strategies- Acknowledge that age and gender may subtly influence motivation; therefore, personalize learning approaches considering learners' profiles to enhance intrinsic motivation and engagement.

Level 5: Value – Parental and Socioeconomic Support

V – Value of Socioeconomic and Parental Background- While parental educational attainment and occupation show no significant relationship with motivation, parental involvement and socioeconomic support can still influence learners' motivation indirectly. Encourage parental engagement and provide material support to learners when possible.

Level 6: Empowerment – Motivational Pedagogies

E – Engaging and Empowering Teaching Methods- Utilize student-centered, motivating pedagogies that empower learners, build confidence, and foster sustained motivation to learn English. This includes creating meaningful, relevant, and interactive learning experiences that align with learners' needs and backgrounds.

The MOTIVE Framework provides a structured and evidence-based approach to enhancing learners' motivation in English language learning by addressing key factors identified in the study. Starting with foundational language responsiveness through multilingual scaffolding, it builds upward by offering inclusive opportunities for translanguaging, tailoring interventions by grade level, and individualizing strategies based on learner profiles. The framework also acknowledges the broader influence of parental and socioeconomic contexts while emphasizing empowering pedagogies that actively engage students. By following this hierarchical model, educators can create a more supportive and motivating learning environment that meets the diverse needs of learners and promotes sustained motivation to master English.

Conclusion

Majority of the participants are female; most of them are within the age range of 13–14; majority are Grade 10 students; Cebuano is the majority's heritage language; most of them prefer Filipino as a medium of instruction; and the majority's socioeconomic status is low. The extent of learners' motivation in learning English is high.

There is no significant relationship between learners' extent of motivation and variables such as age, sex, grade level, heritage language, preferred medium of instruction, parents' highest educational attainment, occupation, and combined monthly income.

Based on these findings, the MOTIVE Framework was developed to offer a structured approach to understanding and enhancing English language learning motivation among last-mile learners. This framework highlights the need to consider learners' cultural and linguistic backgrounds, as well as the challenges they face in remote educational contexts. It serves as a guide for developing learner-centered strategies that sustain and boost motivation in English language learning.

Teachers may consider incorporating translanguaging strategies in teaching English, especially since students' heritage language is not English and their preferred medium of instruction is Filipino. Meeting learners halfway linguistically fosters better engagement and comprehension. However, this approach should still encourage English language use, as it remains central to the subject.

Future researchers may replicate or adapt this study to validate the MOTIVE Framework in other last-mile contexts and explore additional factors that influence learners' motivation in acquiring English proficiency.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that teachers and school leaders utilize the MOTIVE Framework as a guiding tool in designing motivation-enhancing strategies that are responsive to the unique needs of last-mile learners. This framework can inform classroom planning, instructional delivery, and student support initiatives in English language teaching. Given that learners in this study primarily speak Cebuano and prefer Filipino as the medium of instruction, teachers are encouraged to incorporate translanguaging strategies that allow for flexible use of languages in the classroom. This approach promotes better comprehension and engagement while still supporting the gradual development of English proficiency.

Moreover, culturally responsive teaching practices should be adopted to ensure that lessons and materials are relevant to the students' linguistic, cultural, and socioeconomic backgrounds. Creating a learning environment that fosters motivation—through recognition of student effort, meaningful interactions, and supportive feedback—can also contribute to improved outcomes in language learning. To implement these practices effectively, capacity-building workshops should be provided to teachers, focusing on learner motivation, inclusive instruction, and the practical application of the MOTIVE Framework.

Finally, it is recommended that further research be conducted in other rural or last-mile contexts to validate and refine the MOTIVE Framework. Future studies may also explore other motivational

factors not covered in this research, thus broadening the understanding of what drives English language learning among students in geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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